

**Complexes of 2-Substituted-amino-5-(2-furyl)-
1,3,4-thiadiazoles with Cobalt(II),
Nickel(II) and Copper(II)**

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A number of complexes of 2,5-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazoles are known¹. The survey of literature reveals that no work has been done on the metal complexes of 2-phenylamino-5-(2-furyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (L), 2-(*p*-chlorophenyl)amino-5-(2-furyl)-1,3,

4-thiadiazole (L') and 2-(*p*-methylphenyl)amino-5-(2-furyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (L''). The 2,5-substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives are known to possess wide range of biological activities³. By virtue of -N-C-S moiety the toxophoric importance is more stressed on the heterocyclic compounds³. We report here the synthesis and characterisation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with L, L' and L''.

Experimental

The ligands (L, L' and L'') were prepared by the known procedure⁴. The complexes were prepared by mixing hot ethanolic solution of ligand to the ethanolic solution of metal chloride in 1:1 molar ratio and refluxing for ~1 h on a water-bath. The Cu^{II} complexes separated immediately and solid sodium acetate was added with stirring to facilitate complexation in case of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. The separated complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over fused CaCl₂.

The details of the elemental analyses and measurements of magnetic susceptibility, molar conductance, electronic and infrared spectral measurements are described elsewhere.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results indicate that all the complexes are in 1:1 molar ratio except CuL₂Cl₂ and CuL''Cl₂. All the complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMF, DMSO and pyridine.⁵ The molar conductance of the complexes in DMF (10⁻³M) are in the range 7.5–25.50 Ω⁻¹·cm² mol⁻¹ indicating their nonelectrolytic nature. An appreciable value of molar conductance of about 35.0 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ for the Ni^{II} complexes

of ligands L and L'' may be due to solvolysis in DMF. The magnetic moment values 4.35 and 4.2 B.M. observed for CoLCl₂ and CoL'Cl₂ complexes respectively, reveal the tetrahedral nature around Co^{II} ion. A lower μ_{eff} value (2.86 B.M.) for CoL''Cl₂ may be due to polymeric nature of the complex⁶. In the case of the Ni^{II} complexes, μ_{eff} values are in the range 3.01–3.16 B.M. suggesting an octahedral geometry. The observed magnetic moment values for the Cu^{II} complexes show slight deviation from the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) which may be due to the dimeric or polymeric nature with distorted octahedral structure.

The solid state electronic spectral bands for the Co^{II} complexes are around 8 330 (ν₂) and 15 000–16 000 cm⁻¹ (ν₃) for ligands L and L', suggesting tetrahedral geometry. Using Underhill and Billing equation⁶ the values of Dq (487, 493 cm⁻¹), B' (725, 595 cm⁻¹); β (0.75, 0.61), β% (25.0, 38.48); ν₂/ν₁ (1.71, 1.69) and LFSE (16.90 kcal mol⁻¹) are calculated and are suggestive of tetrahedral nature of the complexes. The electronic spectrum of CoL''Cl₂ is a typical of an octahedral stereochemistry⁶ with ν₁ band at 8 333 and ν₃ at 18 180 cm⁻¹. The ligand field parameters (Dq=938 cm⁻¹, B'=726 cm⁻¹, ν₂/ν₁=2.12) are also suggestive of the octahedral structure. The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes exhibit three bands in the region 8 500–25 000 cm⁻¹ in an octahedral field. The ligand field parameters such as Dq (952–869 cm⁻¹), B' (885–682 cm⁻¹), β (0.84–0.69), β% (35.92–30.88); ν₂/ν₁ (1.67–1.61) and LFSE (32.63–29.80 kcal mol⁻¹) values further support the octahedral nature of the complexes. All the Cu^{II} complexes exhibit only one broad asymmetric band at 11 760–16 670 cm⁻¹. The calculated values of Dq (1 400 cm⁻¹) and LFSE (24.76–25.00 kcal mol⁻¹) suggest distorted octahedral geometry⁹.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. cond. Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ _{eff} B.M.
		Metal	N	Cl	S		
CoLCl ₂	195	15.25 (15.79)	11.85 (11.26)	19.50 (19.04)	8.20 (8.58)	7.57	4.35
CoL'Cl ₂	300	14.38 (14.41)	10.55 (10.31)	17.38 (17.43)	8.05 (7.85)	30.15	4.20
CoL''Cl ₂	260	15.60 (15.22)	10.40 (10.85)	18.87 (18.35)	8.57 (8.27)	15.15	2.86
NiLCl ₂	300	15.65 (15.75)	10.85 (11.26)	18.95 (19.05)	8.45 (8.58)	35.10	3.01
NiL'Cl ₂	300	13.85 (14.41)	10.40 (10.31)	16.90 (17.44)	7.40 (7.85)	35.12	3.16
NiL''Cl ₂	300	15.45 (15.22)	10.75 (10.86)	18.35 (18.36)	8.65 (8.27)	10.35	3.14
CuL ₂ Cl ₂	300	10.70 (10.23)	13.45 (13.53)	11.80 (11.44)	9.85 (10.31)	20.18	1.92
CuL'Cl ₂	260d	15.38 (15.41)	9.95 (10.19)	18.05 (17.23)	7.55 (7.76)	25.50	1.93
CuL''Cl ₂	235	9.90 (9.79)	11.45 (12.95)	10.52 (10.44)	9.37 (9.87)	18.25	1.93

The ir spectra (nujol) of the ligands exhibit broad medium intensity bands at 3 400–3 200 and 3 130–3 060 cm^{-1} assignable to ν_{asy} and ν_{sy} NH stretches respectively. These bands shift to lower region by about 170–50 cm^{-1} in case of the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of ligand L suggesting coordination through N atoms of NH group^{7,10}. The medium strong intensity bands observed at 1 605–1 575 cm^{-1} (C=N cyclic) in ligand L practically remained unchanged in the spectra of all the complexes, suggesting non-involvement of thiadiazole ring nitrogen atom in bonding. However, in the ligand L'', the strong intensity $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (cyclic) bands observed at 1 610 and 1 505 cm^{-1} show red-shifts of about 25–10 cm^{-1} in all the complexes suggesting participation of ring nitrogen in bonding with the metal ions. The medium intensity bands observed for ligand L at 1 225 and 1 090 cm^{-1} are assignable to C–O–C (ring) stretch¹¹. These bands undergo blue-shift by about 10–15 cm^{-1} in case of the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes and red-shift by 5–15 cm^{-1} in the Co^{II} complexes suggesting the involvement of oxygen of C–O–C moiety in coordination with Co^{II} ion only. Similar red-shifts are also observed for all the complexes of ligand L'.

The medium intensity bands at 850–670 cm^{-1} observed in free ligands attributable to C–S–C (ring) stretching vibrations¹², show a downward shift with splitting and decreased intensity on complexation suggesting the involvement of ring sulphur in bonding with metal ions.

The bonding through furan ring oxygen in CoLCl_2 and all the complexes of ligand L' is supported by the appearance of non-ligand bands in the region 515–470 cm^{-1} . The bands at 470–415 and 330–305 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ of amino group in NiLCl_2 and CuLCl_2 and of ring vibrations in all the complexes of L'' respectively. In case of the complexes of polymeric nature, the terminal and bridging $\nu_{\text{M-C1}}$ have been assigned at 270–250 and 250–220 cm^{-1} respectively. The $\nu_{\text{M-C1}}$ in other complexes have been attributed in the 260–220 cm^{-1} region. The medium intensity bands observed at 320–270 cm^{-1} have been assigned to M–S stretch in all the complexes.

Biological screening : All the ligands and complexes were screened against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* bacteria using agar plate disk diffusion technique. All the thiadiazole ligands show more activity against *S. aureus* and least activity against *E. coli*; 2-*p*-chlorophenyl derivative and its Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are highly active against *S. aureus* (zone of inhibition 24–26 mm) and the Cu^{II} complex is moderately active. The activity against *S. aureus* increases from ligand (tolyl derivative) to complex and the Cu^{II} complex exhibits maximum inhibitory action (29 mm). All other ligands and complexes exhibit low to moderate activity against both the organisms.

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